

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING OF MULTISCALE CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER (CFRP) COMPOSITES FOR MULTIFUNCTIONALITY

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ABSTRACT

Multiscale carbon-fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites were successfully prepared through the incorporation of conductive carbon-based nanomaterials with different dimensionalities, geometries and surface chemistry. Pristine and functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (*p*- or *f*-MWCNTs) or pristine graphene nanoplatelets (*p*-GnPs) were efficiently dispersed in an epoxy resin using a three-roll mill. Comprehensive rheological, mechanical and electrical studies showed the complexity of selecting the most promising nanofiller for specific applications. While noticeable improvements were found in terms of both elastic modulus (16 %) and ultimate tensile strength (37 %) by modifying the polymeric matrix with 0.043 wt. % of *p*-MWCNTs, minor effects were observed for nanocomposites containing 0.36 or 2.14 wt. % of *p*-GnPs. Afterwards, the most promising formulations were reinforced with carbon fibres to produce pre-impregnated materials that were further converted into CFRP laminates. The interlaminar fracture toughness under mode-I loading (G_{IC}) and the DC electrical conductivities of CFRP composite laminates were evaluated. A noticeable impact of the presence of *p*-GnPs was reflected by an increase of G_{IC} by 70 %.

1 INTRODUCTION

The development of carbon-fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites with enhanced multifunctionality and mechanical performance is highly desirable for several demanding industries, including automotive, defence, aerospace, renewable energy, among others. Currently, CFRP composites have been replacing traditional materials, as metals and alloys, in lightweight structural components owing to their remarkable in-plane properties, allied to advantages related on the manufacturing of complex structural integrated parts [1].

However, damage tolerance is still a major challenge in the design, manufacturing and lifetime of traditional CFRP composites. Boosting by strict requirements on safety and reliability in aerospace applications, CFRP composite parts and structures are typically overdesigned aiming to avoid unexpected internal microscale damages (interfacial debonding or delamination), which hinders the weight reduction purpose of using them. These drawbacks are mainly promoted either by the brittle nature of thermoset resins or by the weak fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion. For those reasons, two strategies have been widely exploited to enhance the poor through-thickness properties of CFRP composites: i) the functionalization of carbon fibres (CFs) surface, or ii) the modification of the polymeric matrices with conductive carbon-based nanostructures, with special focus on carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene and its derivatives.

An overview of the literature reveals that higher resistance against delamination is typically achieved by growing *in situ* aligned carbon nanomaterials onto the surface of fibres or by placing unaligned nanoreinforcements at low volume fraction on fibres and at the plies interface [2]. Garcia *et al.* [3] used dip-coating of CNT growth catalyst and atmospheric-pressure chemical vapour deposition (CVD) of dense aligned CNTs in a fabric woven, which was further impregnated with a thermoset resin. The hybrid architecture allowed significant improvements on the interlaminar shear strength. However, this appealing technology is not very effective in prevent the initiation and propagation of relatively small cracks at the matrix, which can induce the degradation of the in-plane properties of the composites promoted by misalignment, crimp, or fracture of the load-carrying in-plane fibres [4]. In addition, it is time-consuming, expensive and oriented to batch-scale production.

The modification of polymeric matrices with nanoreinforcements allows the development of morphologies at the nanoscale that control the fracture behaviour of CFRP composites by introducing additional energy dissipation mechanisms, such as crack-bridging, crack pinning, voiding growth of the matrix and cracking deflection [REF], improving their damage tolerance. According to the literature, enhancements on the mechanical and electrical performance can be attained at ultralow content of fillers, since homogeneous dispersion and a strong interface are ensured. R. M. Santos *et al.* [5] developed nano-enabled multifunctional CFRP composites using a pre-impregnation strategy and an increase of 44 % on G_{IC} was reported by just incorporating of 0.043 wt. % of functionalized CNTs with pyrrolidine and benzyl carbamate groups.

Although CNTs and graphene nanoplatelets (GnPs) are constituted by similar building blocks (sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms arranged in a lattice), the different dimensionalities and geometries of CNTs (one dimensional, 1D rod-like) and GnPs (two dimensional, 2D sheet-like) have a crucial impact on the viscosity, electrical percolation threshold and mechanical performance of the final polymer systems [6]. While higher electrical conductivities are typically achieved through the incorporation of CNTs, milder effects on the viscosity are found with flat GnPs.

In this work, the effects of carbon-based nanomaterials having different dimensionalities, geometries and surface chemistry on the processability and ultimate properties of multiscale CFRP composites were investigated. Epoxy-based suspensions containing different loadings of pristine and functionalized CNTs or pristine GnPs were prepared using a small-scale three-roll mill, which generate strong hydrodynamic stresses able to disperse and individualize remaining agglomerates. Afterwards, modified suspensions were reinforced with carbon fibres (CFs) using a laboratory drumwinder to produce pre-impregnated materials that were converted into laminated composites using an autoclave.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PART

2.1 MATERIALS

Araldite LY556[®] (Huntsman Corporation, Germany) an epoxy resin based on diglycidylether of bisphenol A, with a viscosity at 25 °C of 10000-12000 mPa·s, density of 1.15 to 1.2 g·cm⁻³ and an epoxide index of 5.30 to 5.45 eq·Kg⁻¹, was used as pre-polymer matrix. The pre-mixture (aradur 1571[®] and accelerator 1573[®], Huntsman Corporation, Germany) and the hardener XB 3403[®] (Huntsman Corporation, Germany) were combined with the resin using a mechanical stirrer at 1000 rpm during 15 minutes, for the production of pre-impregnated sheets.

According to the manufacturer (XG Sciences, USA), graphene nanoplatelets xGnP-Grade M[®] have a thickness of approximately 6 to 8 nm, an average diameter of 5 to 25 μm and a typical average surface area of 120 to 150 m²·g⁻¹. They are supply in powder form with a bulk density of 0.03 to 0.1 g·cm⁻³. Thin multi-walled carbon nanotubes, NC 7000[®] (Nanocyl, Belgium), produced by the catalytic chemical vapor deposition (CCVD) process, have an average diameter of 9.5 nm, an average length of 1.5 μm, a surface area of 250 to 300 m²·g⁻¹ and a bulk density of 0.066 g·cm⁻³. CNTs were chemically modified *via* 1.3 dipolar cycloaddition of azomethine ylides under mild reaction conditions, as reported elsewhere [5].

High strength/standard modulus aerospace carbon fibres, Tenax E HTA40 E13[®] (Toho Tenax, Germany), with 6k tow size were used for manufacturing of pre-impregnated materials and CFRP

composites. This grade is produced from polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor and its surface is treated to promote a good adhesion with polymeric matrices.

2.2 EPOXY-BASED SUSPENSIONS AND NANOCOMPOSITES

The modified epoxy-based suspensions with different carbon-based nanoparticles were produced with a three rolls-mill (EXAKT 80[®], EXAKT Technologies Inc.), at room temperature. This intensive mixer consists of three adjacent cylindrical rolls rotating with an angular velocity ratio of 1:3:9, which allows the fine control of the dispersion degree by changing the gap width between the rolls and rotational speed of the rolls. In this work, a rotational speed of 200 rpm was used and the gap widths were set to provide a constant mass flow for each milling cycle. A progressive increase of the nominal shear rates, from 28.000 to 220.000 s⁻¹, was applied by a stepwise reduction of the gap widths.

The rheological behavior of the epoxy resin and its modified suspensions was assessed on a Discovery hybrid rheometer DHR-1[®] (TA instruments), using a parallel plate geometry with a diameter of 25 mm and gap less than 1 mm, at 25 °C. Small amplitude oscillatory shear, SAOS, experiments were performed to the samples at an angular frequency sweep from 0.01 to 10 rad·s⁻¹. Before experiments took place, the samples were pre-equilibrated at 1 Hz with a deformation of 0.1% during 300 s. All rheological measurements were carried out before the addition of hardener or accelerator.

The DC electrical conductivities of epoxy-based nanocomposites were calculated from the slope of *I* vs. *V* curves measured using an automated Keithley 487[®] picoammeter/voltage source, with an applied voltage ranging between -10 and 10 V, at room temperature. Electrodes with 50 nm thicknesses of gold/palladium mixture were deposited onto sample surface by magnetron sputtering using a Polaron SC502[®] sputter coater, to ensure a good contact. Geometrical parameters were used to calculate the resistivity (ρ) of the samples, which was then converted to electrical conductivity (σ_{DC}) in S·m⁻¹.

Tensile experiments of the epoxy-based nanocomposites were obtained from dog-bone specimens according to ISO 527-2, using an INSTRON 4208[®] universal instrument with a load cell of 5 kN and a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm·min⁻¹.

2.3 MANUFACTURING OF PRE-IMPREGNATED MATERIALS AND COMPOSITES

The procedure used for manufacturing multiscale CFRP composites involved three main steps. Firstly, epoxy-based suspensions were prepared by forcing a premixture of polymer and nanofiller through a three-roll mill, under optimized mixing conditions as described previously in section 2.2. Secondly, unidirectional (UD) pre-impregnated sheets with dimensions of 0.3 x 1.5 m were produced using a laboratory drumwinder, under well-defined conditions. Thirdly, the UD prepreg sheets were cut into smaller sections and CFRP panels were fabricated by means of hand-stacking in a 0° orientation. After the layup, CFRP laminates were cured in a vacuum bag using an autoclave, at 120 °C and 3.5 bar for 2 hours.

2.4 PRE-IMPREGNATED MATERIALS AND COMPOSITES CHARACTERIZATION

Double cantilever beam (DCB) experiments were carried out using the same apparatus and the crack-opening load was applied at a crosshead rate of 0.5 mm·min⁻¹. The DCB specimens comprising 32 layers were prepared according to ASTM D5528-01: a teflon film was inserted between the 16th and 17th plies, in order to create an initial pre-crack of 65 mm. The interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IC}) under mode I loading was determined using a modified beam theory [7]. The flexural (E_f) and shear (G_{13}) modulus were determined using a three-point bending (ASTM D790) and tensile at $\pm 45^\circ$ (ASTM D3518) tests, respectively.

The DC electrical conductivities of CFRP composites were evaluated using a similar procedure to that described in section 2.2.

3 RESULTS

3.1 EPOXY-BASED SUSPENSIONS AND NANOCOMPOSITES

The incorporation of carbon-based nanomaterials can significantly alter the flow behaviour of the epoxy resin, playing a crucial role on its processability limit due to the increments in the viscosity [8]. Fig. 1 shows the complex viscosity ($|\eta^*|$) and storage modulus (G') behaviour of epoxy-based suspensions containing different loadings of 1D-MWCNTs and 2D-GnPs.

Figure 1: complex viscosity ($|\eta^*|$) and storage modulus (G') behaviour of epoxy-based suspensions containing different loadings of 1D-MWCNTs [a), b)] and 2D-GnPs [c), d)], respectively.

Due to its low molecular weight, the neat epoxy resin shows a Newtonian behaviour as indicated by the non-dependency of the complex viscosity on the angular frequency [9]. It is interesting to note that the viscosity curves for epoxy-based suspensions containing 0.06 and 0.13 wt. % of *p*-MWCNTs have a similar frequency dependencies as the neat epoxy [Fig. 1 a)]. At higher loadings, a transition from a liquid-like to solid-like viscoelastic behaviour and a strong shear thinning effect were observed, suggesting that a nanotube network fine dispersed was formed. Interconnected structures of anisometric nanofillers result in an apparent yield stress, which is visible in dynamic measurements by a plateau of storage modulus (G') vs. frequency at low frequencies [Fig. 1 b)]. As the *p*-MWCNTs loading increases, the shear thinning effect becomes more pronounced especially at low angular frequencies, due to the higher number of nanotube-nanotube or polymer-nanotube interactions [10]. On the other hand, GnPs does not change the Newtonian regime of the epoxy resin because the interfacial bonding established between the nanofiller and the resin is weaker [Fig. 1 c) and d)]. Their flat morphology enables them to slide over one another in the event of filler-filler interaction [6].

The DC electrical conductivities of the epoxy resin and its nanocomposites are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Electrical conductivities of epoxy-based nanocomposites containing different loadings of *p*-MWCNTs, *f*-MWCNTs and *p*-GnPs.

At ultralow contents, the incorporation of *p*-MWCNTs promotes an increase of 6 orders of magnitude on the DC electrical conductivity in comparison with epoxy resin ($1.2 \times 10^{-11} \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$). Upon 0.18 wt. % of *p*-MWCNTs, a constant plateau is reached with a maximum value of $0.002 \text{ S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$. Slightly differences on the electrical conductivity of epoxy-based nanocomposites containing *f*-MWCNTs were found due to the disruption of the long-range conjugated framework of the graphitic lattice (modifications from sp^2 to sp^3 hybridization), leading to a loss of the carrier mobility of MWCNTs. Lower electrical conductivities were attained for epoxy/*p*-GnPs nanocomposites, even when higher loadings of *p*-GnPs are used, corresponding which correspond to a semi-conductive material in the range of electrostatic dissipation [11]. This higher percolation threshold is related to the low intrinsic electrical conductivity and aspect ratio of the nanofiller.

Moreover, the mechanical properties of epoxy resin and its based nanocomposites were evaluated. The representative stress-strain curves are depicted in Fig. 3 and the results summarized in Table 1.

Figure 3: Representative stress-strain curves of the epoxy resin and its nanocomposites.

Formulation	Young's modulus (MPa)	Improvements (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Improvements (%)
<i>Epoxy</i>	2885±206	-	47±5	-
<i>Epoxy/0.043 wt.% p-MWCNTs</i>	3338±167	16	64±6	37
<i>Epoxy/0.043 wt.% f-MWCNTs</i>	3520±176	22	73±4	56
<i>Epoxy/0.357 wt.% p-GnPs</i>	2991±60.8	3.6	51±3	9.0

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the epoxy matrix and its nanocomposites.

The incorporation of carbon-based nanoreinforcements having different geometric features and surface chemistry showed a different level of enhancing trend compared to the epoxy resin (baseline). While noticeable improvements of young's modulus and tensile strength were found for epoxy-based nanocomposites containing *p*- (16 and 37%) or *f*-MWCNTs (22 and 56%), only moderate enhancements were attained through the incorporation of higher loadings of *p*-GnPs (3.6 and 9.0%). The less promising reinforcement efficiency of *p*-GnPs can be explained by the presence of a higher number or larger GnP agglomerates, acting as defects or microcenters of stress concentration and restricting the load transfer from the reinforcement to polymeric matrix [12].

3.2 MULTISCALE CFRP COMPOSITES

Aiming to evaluate the effects of different carbon-based nanomaterials on the ability of CFRP composites to resist interply delamination under a normal force perpendicular to the crack plane, DCB testing was performed. The representative load vs. displacement curves of CFRP composites, depicted in Fig. 4 a), are characterized by stick-slips due to the variations in local material properties, such as resin-rich or fibre-rich regions, misalignment of fibres, fracture of bridged fibres or fibre bundles [13].

Figure 4: Representative load vs. displacement curves a) and resistance (R) curves b) of CFRP composites, respectively.

For unmodified and modified CFRPs with 0.043 wt. % of p -MWCNTs, a linear elastic behaviour up to the maximum load can be noticed, followed by a gradual decrease as the crack further propagated. For multiscale composites containing f -MWCNTs or p -GnPs, after the crack initiation point, a further increase in load was systematically observed, revealing the positive influence of these nanofillers on the fracture process and fracture performance of CFRPs. Additional energy absorbed mechanisms are activated within the process zone ahead and behind the main crack tip, especially with the incorporation of GnPs, which are responsible for a slower and smother crack propagation [14]. The G_{IC} was determined at crack propagation plateau of R -curves, until a steady-state value is reached. Table 2 summarizes the G_{IC} improvements attained through the incorporation of p - and f -MWCNTs or p -GnPs of CFRP composites.

Formulation	G_{IC} ($N \cdot mm^{-1}$)	Improvements (%)
<i>Unmodified CFRP</i>	0.207 ± 0.008	-
<i>CFRP/0.043 wt.% p-MWCNTs</i>	0.230 ± 0.011	11
<i>CFRP/0.043 wt.% f-MWCNTs</i>	0.298 ± 0.015	44
<i>CFRP/0.357 wt.% p-GnPs</i>	0.259 ± 0.008	25
<i>CFRP/2.14 wt.% p-GnPs</i>	0.401 ± 0.009	70

Table 2: The interlaminar fracture toughness under mode I (G_{IC}) improvements of CFRP composites.

It is evident that significant improvements were achieved for both multiscale CFRP composites containing CNTs with tailored interfaces (up to +44%) and p -GnPs (up to +70%) in comparison with unmodified CFRP composite, owing to the additional toughening/energy dissipation mechanisms that are introduced during the crack propagation.

The electrical conductivity of conventional CFRPs are typically $\sim 1^{-1}-10^{-2}$ in the in-plane, $10^{-3}-10^{-2}$ in the through-thickness and $10^{-1} S \cdot cm^{-1}$ in the volume directions [15], showing their highly anisotropic behavior. Significant improvements in the DC volume electrical conductivity of CFRP composites were attained (from 5.57×10^{-3} to $4.45 \times 10^{-2} S \cdot m^{-1}$) through the incorporation of 0.043 wt.% of p -MWCNTs or 2.14 wt. % of p -GnPs, as it can be seen in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: DC volume electrical conductivities of multiscale CFRP composites.

The electrical conductivity of CFRP composites performed in the cross-fibre direction is strongly dependent on the random contacts between the fibres, since it is assumed that the current flows a stochastic zigzag path across the fibre-to-fibre contacts [16]. Therefore, the improvements observed were promoted by an increase of the electrical pathways formed within the interlaminar regions.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, epoxy resin formulations containing 1D-MWCNTs and 2D-GnPs were investigated in terms of their mechanical, rheological and electrical properties. The formulations presenting the most promising results were subsequently transferred for the production of multiscale CFRP composites. The presence of *p*- or *f*-MWCNTs have shown a noticeable enhancement of the mechanical and electrical properties of the polymeric matrix compared to formulations containing higher loading of *p*-GnPs. In turn, carbon-based nanomaterials having a layered structure seem to be the most suitable for enhancing the damage tolerance of CFRP composites. Strong improvements were observed in the crack propagation of multiscale CFRP composites, especially those containing either MWCNTs with tailored interfaces (44 %) or *p*-GnPs (70 %), promoted by the presence of additional toughening/energy dissipation mechanisms. In the particular case of CFRPs containing *f*-MWCNTs, the improvement attained is remarkable considering that it only contains 0.043 wt.% of nanoparticle loading. Unfortunately, higher loadings could not be obtained since MWCNTs drastically potentiates the increase of resin viscosity, turning processability difficult.

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